

Comparative analysis of the Bulgarian national therapeutic guideline on breast cancer treatment with the NCCN, ASCO, and ESMO guidelines using the PICO methodology and its relevance to patient access

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Abstract

Objectives: Patient-centric healthcare ecosystems prioritize personalized diagnostics and treatments based on high-quality evidence regarding health technologies. Pharmacotherapeutic guidelines are essential for providing evidence-based recommendations, enhancing patient safety, and aligning healthcare policies with early detection and rational drug use.

Methods: This study compares the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on breast cancer with the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN), American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO), and European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) guidelines using the Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome (PICO) methodology, assessing alignment in screening, pharmacotherapy, follow-up, outcomes, and shared decision-making.

Results: The results show that Bulgaria has a unified set of guidelines for tumor locations but lacks specific recommendations for screening and shared decision-making. While these guidelines align closely with international standards for breast cancer treatment, they do not offer guidance on follow-up, outcomes, or genomic profiling. Importantly, they incorporate new therapies before these are added to the Positive Drug List, thereby influencing regulatory decisions and patient access to treatments.

Conclusion: The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on breast cancer aligns with international standards but could be improved with respect to screening, early detection, therapy adherence, and shared decision-making. A structured classification for levels of evidence would also enhance the guidelines.

Keywords

Guidelines, oncology, patient access, PICO

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) ranks breast cancer as the most diagnosed cancer worldwide and a leading cause of mortality among women (Wilkinson and Gathani 2022). In response to the latest global cancer statistics, the WHO launched the Global Breast Cancer Initiative in 2021, aiming to address the global health challenge of breast cancer by improving survival rates worldwide. The initiative focuses on three key pillars: 1) health promotion, 2) screening and timely diagnosis, and 3) comprehensive treatment and supportive care (World Health Organization 2017).

In this context, clinical practice guidelines play a crucial role in offering evidence-based recommendations that facilitate effective health promotion strategies. They serve as a framework for the implementation of screening programs and diagnostic procedures, ensuring that these initiatives are conducted systematically and optimally. Moreover, these guidelines help identify the most effective treatment regimens by considering both clinical efficacy and economic viability. By integrating research findings and expert consensus, clinical practice guidelines not only enhance patient care but also contribute to improved resource allocation within healthcare systems, ultimately leading to better health outcomes. A recently published systematic review on evidence-based clinical practice guidelines for breast cancer showed that multiple guidelines are available worldwide, but there is a need to evaluate the evidence of their benefits in improving the quality of care. Based on the systematic review using the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome) methodology, the authors suggested a need for a more balanced approach between the number of high-quality studies and the increasing number of emerging evidence-based guidelines (Ramírez-Morera et al. 2022).

The PICO methodology offers a structured approach to formulating clinical questions and enhancing evidence-based practice. When applied to pharmacotherapeutic guidelines, it can significantly improve the quality, clarity, and relevance of the recommendations provided (Huang et al. 2006).

The current study aims to compare the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on breast cancer with the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN), American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO), and European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) guidelines using the PICO methodology, assessing alignment in screening, pharmacotherapy, follow-up, outcomes, and shared decision-making.

Methods and materials

We performed a comparative descriptive analysis of the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline for breast cancer alongside the NCCN, ASCO, and ESMO guidelines (Table 1), using the PICO methodology (Table 2), with a primary focus on pharmacotherapy alignment.

Furthermore, we evaluated the possible inclusion of recommendations for screening, follow-up, outcomes, and shared decision-making.

Results

PICO methodology-based comparative analysis

The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on medical oncology categorizes patient populations primarily based on the type of treatment administered—namely, neoadjuvant, adjuvant, and systemic therapies. The guideline specifically addresses populations associated with various cancer types and locations, including triple-negative breast cancer, inflammatory carcinoma (carcinomatous mastitis), breast cancer with low HER2 expression, and male breast cancer. It is noteworthy that, although these populations are classified according to cancer type, the guideline does not provide additional disease-related parameters beyond the therapeutic approach. In contrast, the populations outlined in the ESMO and NCCN guidelines are categorized according to cancer type. The ESMO guidelines encompass several specific populations, including early-stage breast cancer, metastatic breast cancer, breast cancer in young women, and considerations for risk reduction and screening in hereditary breast-ovarian cancer syndromes. Conversely, the NCCN guidelines classify populations into three broad categories: non-invasive breast cancer, invasive breast cancer, and special considerations. The populations addressed in the ASCO guidelines focus on both treatment type (neoadjuvant, adjuvant, systemic, endocrine, targeted, and integrative therapies) and cancer type (early breast cancer, high-risk early breast cancer, hormone receptor-positive, human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-negative metastatic breast cancer, metastatic breast cancer, hormone receptor-negative metastatic breast cancer, high-risk early-stage triple-negative breast cancer, high-risk early-stage HER2-negative breast cancer, male breast cancer, and hereditary breast cancer). Overall, the ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO guidelines contain comprehensive information.

With respect to interventions, the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline provides recommendations specifically for drug therapy and offers high-level guidance on surgical treatment. In contrast, the ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO guidelines encompass a broader scope, offering recommendations for drug therapy, surgical interventions, and radiotherapy.

Treatment recommendations categorized by pharmacological class are consistent across the Bulgarian, ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO guidelines.

The outcomes monitored across all pharmacotherapeutic guidelines demonstrate a high degree of alignment; a minor difference is observed in the ASCO measures of quality of life (QoL) in certain recommendations. For example, this divergence is evident in the “*Systemic*

Table 1. Data source.

Region of application	Document	Source
Bulgaria (BG)	Pharmacotherapeutic guideline on medical oncology (BG PhTher Guideline 2022) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neoadjuvant systemic therapy • Adjuvant systemic therapy • Systemic therapy for relapsed or metastatic disease • Triple-negative breast cancer • Inflammatory carcinoma (carcinomatous mastitis) • Breast cancer with low HER2 expression • Breast cancer in men 	National Council of Prices and Reimbursement – https://www.ncpr.bg/images/farmako-terapevtichni/PharmTher-onkologia_2018_dopaln._293_pr._23.08.2018__version-J21.pdf
European Union (EU)	ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines: breast cancer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early breast cancer (Cardoso et al. 2019); • Metastatic breast cancer (Gennari et al. 2021) • Breast cancer in young women (Paluch-Shimon et al. 2020); • Risk reduction and screening of cancer in hereditary breast-ovarian cancer syndromes (Sessa et al. 2023); 	European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) – https://www.esmo.org/guidelines/esmo-clinical-practice-guidelines-breast-cancer
USA	NCCN Clinical Practice Guidelines: breast cancer v.4.2025 (NCCN 2025a) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noninvasive breast cancer (NCCN 2025) • Invasive breast cancer (NCCN 2025b) • Special consideration (NCCN 2025): breast cancer during pregnancy, inflammatory breast cancer, Paget disease, phyllodes tumor; ASCO Clinical Practice Guidelines: breast cancer (ASCO Publications 2025) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early breast cancer (Park et al. 2025; Freedman et al. 2024) • High-risk early breast cancer (Freedman et al. 2022) • Hormone receptor–positive, human epidermal growth factor receptor 2–negative metastatic breast cancer (Burstain et al. 2024) • Metastatic breast cancer (Al Sukhun et al. 2024) • Hormone receptor–negative metastatic breast cancer (Moy et al. 2023) • High-risk early-stage triple-negative breast cancer (Korde et al. 2022) • High-risk early breast cancer (Giordano et al. 2021) • High-risk early-stage HER2-negative breast cancer (Tung et al. 2021) • Male breast cancer (ASCO 2020) • Hereditary breast cancer (ASCO 2021) 	National Comprehensive Cancer Network – https://www.nccn.org/guidelines-detail?category=1&id=1419 ; www.nccn.org ; American Society of Clinical Oncology – https://ascopubs.org/topics/asco-guidelines/breast-cancer

Table 2. PICO-based comparative analysis.

	BG PhTher Guideline	ESMO	NCCN	ASCO
P- Population	General; focused on treatment type	Cancer type–specific	Cancer type–specific	Focused on treatment type; cancer type–specific
I-Intervention	Drug therapy; surgery	Drug therapy; surgery; radiotherapy	Drug therapy; surgery; radiotherapy	Drug therapy; surgery; radiotherapy
C-Comparators	CDK4/6 inhibitors; chemotherapy; endocrine therapy; aromatase inhibitors; PARP inhibitors; HER2+ inhibitors; tyrosine kinase inhibitors; PD-L1 inhibitors; bisphosphonates; AKT/PI3KCA/PTEN inhibitors; monoclonal antibodies	CDK4/6 inhibitors; chemotherapy; endocrine therapy; aromatase inhibitors; PARP inhibitors; HER2+ inhibitors; tyrosine kinase inhibitors; PD-L1 inhibitors; bisphosphonates; AKT/PI3KCA/PTEN inhibitors; monoclonal antibodies	CDK4/6 inhibitors; chemotherapy; endocrine therapy; aromatase inhibitors; PARP inhibitors; HER2+ inhibitors; tyrosine kinase inhibitors; PD-L1 inhibitors; bisphosphonates; AKT/PI3KCA/PTEN inhibitors; monoclonal antibodies	CDK4/6 inhibitors; chemotherapy; endocrine therapy; aromatase inhibitors; PARP inhibitors; HER2+ inhibitors; tyrosine kinase inhibitors; PD-L1 inhibitors; bisphosphonates; AKT/PI3KCA/PTEN inhibitors; monoclonal antibodies
O-Outcomes	Overall survival (OS); progression-free survival (PFS); disease-free survival (DFS)	Overall survival (OS); progression-free survival (PFS); disease-free survival (DFS)	Overall survival (OS); progression-free survival (PFS); disease-free survival (DFS)	Overall survival (OS); progression-free survival (PFS); disease-free survival (DFS); quality of life (QoL)

Treatment of Patients with Metastatic Breast Cancer: ASCO Resource-Stratified Guideline.”

The pharmacotherapeutic guidelines issued by the NCCN and ASCO require users to register to access their

full content. This contrasts with the guidelines provided by the ESMO and those established in Bulgaria, which are available without registration. The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guidelines primarily emphasize treatment

strategies, in contrast to other guidelines that incorporate detailed descriptions of diagnosis, pathology, molecular biology, and other disease-related parameters (Table 3). The ESMO guidelines also include epidemiology and incidence data. The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guidance on breast cancer is consolidated into a single document that addresses all solid tumors, in contrast to other guidelines, which are presented across multi-

ple documents and publications focusing specifically on breast cancer. ASCO provides an AI guidelines assistant that supports navigation through the source material. The NCCN offers specific guidelines for patients, which represents a major difference compared with the Bulgarian, ESMO, and ASCO guidelines.

The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guidelines differ from those of other organizations, such as ESMO, ASCO,

Table 3. Additional comparative indicators.

Guideline	Structure (location specific, etc.)	Screening	Treatment	Adherence to therapy indicators	Palliative care	Follow up	Shared decision making (SDM)
NCCN	Member only; multisource. Levels of evidence included Guidelines for patients	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
ASCO	Members only. Multisource. Levels of evidence included. AI assistant	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y
ESMO	Open access. Multisource. Levels of evidence included	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y
Bulgarian PhTer Guideline	Open access; one source. No levels of evidence	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N

Y – available in the guideline.

N – not available in the guideline.

and NCCN, in that they do not specify distinct levels of evidence for their recommendations. In contrast, the ESMO, ASCO, and NCCN guidelines employ structured classification systems that delineate the levels of evidence supporting their pharmacotherapeutic recommendations. The classification criteria used by these organizations are described in Tables 4, 5, 6.

Many of the recommendations put forth in the guidelines are Category 2A. Where categories are not specified within the guidelines, the default designation for the recommendation is Category 2A.

The current Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on medical oncology does not encompass screening recommendations. However, these recommendations are detailed in a separate document, namely the National Cancer Control Plan (Ministry of Health 2023), which aligns with the guidelines established by ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO.

All pharmacotherapeutic guidelines for breast cancer provide comprehensive recommendations for treatment algorithms tailored to the specific characteristics of the disease. Furthermore, these guidelines exhibit a high degree of comparability in their recommendations.

Table 4. NCCN categories of level of evidence and consensus (NCCN 2025).

NCCN categories of the level of evidence and consensus	Description
1	Based on high-level evidence (≥ 1 randomized phase 3 trials or high-quality, robust meta-analyses), there is uniform NCCN consensus ($\geq 85\%$ support of the Panel) that the intervention is appropriate.
2A	Based on lower-level evidence, there is uniform NCCN consensus ($\geq 85\%$ support of the Panel) that the intervention is appropriate.
2B	Based on lower-level evidence, there is NCCN consensus ($\geq 50\%$ but $< 85\%$ support of the Panel) that the intervention is appropriate.
C	Based on any level of evidence, there is major NCCN disagreement that the intervention is appropriate.

Table 5. ASCO uses the GRADE evidence framework when developing guidelines (ASCO 2025).

Quality of evidence	Description
High	We are very confident that the true effect lies close to the estimate of the effect.
Moderate	We are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.
Low	Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
Very low	We have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.

Table 6. ESMO's levels of evidence and grades of recommendations (ESMO 2025).

Levels of evidence	
I	Evidence from at least one large randomized, controlled trial of good methodological quality (low potential for bias) or meta-analyses of well-conducted randomized trials without heterogeneity.
II	Small randomized trials or large randomized trials with a suspicion of bias (lower methodological quality) or meta-analyses of such trials or trials with demonstrated heterogeneity.
III	Prospective cohort studies.
IV	Retrospective cohort studies or case-control studies.
V	Studies without a control group, case reports, or expert opinions.
Grades of recommendation	
A	Strong evidence for efficacy with a substantial clinical benefit; strongly recommended.
B	Strong or moderate evidence for efficacy, but with a limited clinical benefit; generally recommended.
C	Insufficient evidence for efficacy or benefit does not outweigh the risk or disadvantages (adverse events, costs); optional.
D	Moderate evidence against efficacy or for adverse outcomes; generally not recommended.
E	Strong evidence against efficacy or for adverse outcomes; never recommended.

Recommendations regarding adherence to therapy are found exclusively in the NCCN guidelines.

Palliative care and follow-up recommendations are incorporated into all pharmacotherapeutic guidelines, except those provided by ASCO.

Shared decision-making is addressed exclusively in the NCCN and ASCO guidelines and, for metastatic breast cancer, in the ESMO guidelines.

The results show that the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on medical oncology is closely aligned with international standards for breast cancer treatment and includes valuable guidance on follow-up care, patient outcomes, and comprehensive genomic profiling.

The guideline provides a cohesive framework for tumor locations; however, there is a notable absence of specific recommendations regarding screening procedures and shared decision-making between patients and healthcare providers.

A critical aspect of these guidelines is their proactive incorporation of new therapies prior to their inclusion in the Positive Drug List. This approach plays a significant role in shaping regulatory decisions and enhancing patient access to innovative treatments.

Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first study comparing national and international guidelines using the PICO methodology.

Recent national studies have examined pharmacotherapeutic guidelines for multiple sclerosis and advanced breast cancer, comparing them with international standards. These comparisons primarily focus on therapy regimens and the assessment of compliance indices. Regarding adherence to international guidelines, the pharmacotherapeutic instructions for advanced breast cancer in Bulgaria align with the treatment recommendations set forth by the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) and the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) (Karanyotova et al. 2023). Analyses of pharmacotherapeutic guidelines have shown a High Guidelines Compliance Index (GCI) with international guidelines,

again with a primary focus on pharmacotherapy (Seitaridou et al. 2021).

A study published in 2013 compared the treatment recommendations of the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) and the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) for cancer care using the PICO methodology. The results indicated a high level of agreement between the two guidelines while also highlighting specific areas of discordance. Notably, differences were identified between ESMO and NCCN regarding first-line chemotherapy for localized colon cancer and the use of radiotherapy in elderly breast cancer patients (Gao et al. 2013).

Results from the PICO comparison demonstrate that the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on medical oncology shows a high level of comparability with the ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO guidelines across the assessed parameters. The ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO guidelines can be challenging to navigate due to the dispersion of information across multiple publications. In contrast, the Bulgarian guideline consolidates relevant information into a single document, facilitating easier access and comprehension for healthcare professionals. The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline is primarily focused on therapeutic interventions, whereas the ESMO, NCCN, and ASCO guidelines serve as comprehensive resources encompassing a broader range of disease-related information. The ESMO guidelines include data on epidemiology and incidence, the NCCN guidelines provide detailed treatment algorithms specific to various disease subtypes, and the ASCO guidelines offer guidance on specific biomarkers relevant to treatment decisions.

The inclusion of specified levels of evidence in the Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guidelines could provide significant benefits for healthcare professionals. By adopting a structured classification system similar to those used by ESMO, ASCO, and NCCN, the guidelines would offer clearer insight into the strength and reliability of recommendations. This transparency would facilitate informed clinical decision-making and promote adherence to guidelines, as practitioners often seek assurance that their practices are grounded in robust evidence. Ultimately, such an

enhancement could lead to improved patient outcomes by aligning Bulgarian practice more closely with international standards in oncology and pharmacotherapy.

The exclusive inclusion of recommendations regarding adherence to therapy in the NCCN guidelines underscores the critical role that treatment adherence plays in optimizing patient outcomes in breast cancer management. Adherence to prescribed therapies is essential for achieving desired therapeutic effects, reducing the risk of disease progression, and improving overall survival. By providing clear guidance on adherence, the NCCN emphasizes the need for healthcare providers to actively engage patients in their treatment plans, fostering a collaborative approach that enhances patient understanding and commitment to therapy. The absence of similar recommendations in other pharmacotherapeutic guidelines may hinder the implementation of effective adherence strategies, potentially compromising treatment efficacy.

The emphasis on shared decision-making in the American pharmacotherapeutic guidelines—specifically those developed by NCCN and ASCO—highlights the importance of patient engagement in the treatment process. Shared decision-making fosters a collaborative environment in which healthcare providers and patients can discuss treatment options, weigh benefits and risks, and consider patient preferences and values. This approach not only empowers patients but also enhances adherence to therapy, as patients are more likely to commit to treatment plans they have actively helped shape. The absence of similar recommendations in other pharmacotherapeutic guidelines may limit opportunities for improved treatment outcomes, as patient involvement is essential for ensuring that therapies are both clinically effective and aligned with individual patient needs. Broader adoption of shared decision-making principles across pharmacotherapeutic guidelines is therefore essential for optimizing outcomes and enhancing the overall quality of oncology care.

It should also be noted that the Bulgarian guideline is intentionally pharmacotherapeutic in scope, unlike the ESMO, ASCO, and NCCN guidelines, which function as broad clinical guidelines. While it does not encompass the full range of diagnostic and care pathways, treating oncologists may integrate additional clinical considerations as needed, often drawing on ESMO recommendations for breast cancer management. Importantly, the Bulgarian guideline serves a critical regulatory function by enabling reimbursement of novel therapies included in the national Positive Drug List, thereby facilitating timely patient access to approved treatments. This alignment of regulatory objectives with clinical practice supports coherent, evidence-informed care within the Bulgarian healthcare system.

One of the major limitations of the current study is that it provides a general overview of breast cancer guidelines. A more detailed and disease subtype-specific comparison could offer a more precise assessment of compliance levels and identify gaps in international recommendations.

Conclusion

The Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guideline on medical oncology, with a focus on breast cancer, aligns well with international standards for treatment and follow-up care. However, opportunities for improvement remain in screening protocols, early detection, therapy adherence, and shared decision-making, which are closely related to pharmacotherapy and could further enhance patient outcomes. Additionally, incorporating a structured classification system for levels of evidence would strengthen the guidelines.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Elina Petrova contributed to the conceptualization, methodology design, data analysis, and manuscript drafting. Maria Dimitrova and Georgi Momekov contributed to the supervision, critical revision of the manuscript, validation of comparative methodology, and interpretation of results. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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